

D-WP1.1 Kick-off meeting in Italy (IZSAM)

JRP16-ET2.2-TELE-Vir-WP1.1

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: IZSAM

KICK-OFF MEETING IN ITALY (IZSAM)

Summary

The kick off meeting of the TELE-Vir project were held on January 21st – 22nd 2020 at the International Centre for Veterinary Training and Information "F. Gramenzi" (CIFIV) of Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise "G. Caporale" (Via G. Caporale, Teramo, Italy). All partners were present. The OHEJP rules, OHEJP regulations, TELE-Vir project proposal, TELE-Vir deliverables, TELE-Vir tasks and participating Institutes were presented (see Agenda). After the presentations two groups were formed: 1) a Bioinformatic group that discussed WP2 of the TELE-Vir project and 2) a Laboratory group that discussed WP3 of the TELE-Vir project. Each group came up with a Strategic work plan for the TELE-Vir project.

1. Meeting Venue

The International Centre for Veterinary Training and Information (CIFIV) is a training facility founded to facilitate knowledge dissemination and exchange among professionals from cross border countries as well as the Mediterranean basin and Balkan area.

CIFIV is not only a physical centre, but it is also a network of competent authorities, universities and research institutions of east European countries and Mediterranean countries focused on regional approach, strategies and methods to develop health and food safety management systems overcoming individualities.

2. Agenda

2.1. Meeting agenda – January 21st 2020

TIMETABLE	TOPIC	EXPERT
09.00 – 09.10	Welcome	<i>Alessio Lorusso</i>
09.10 – 09.50	OHEJP consortium, rules and guidelines	<i>Maiken W. Rosenstjerne</i>
09.50 – 10.00	Vision of the TELE-Vir project	<i>Anders Fomsgaard</i>
10.00 – 10.40	Outline of the TELE-Vir project	<i>Maiken W. Rosenstjerne</i>
10.40 – 11.00	<i>Group picture</i>	
11.00 – 11.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
11.30 – 11.45	INIA-CISA and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Jovita Fernández Pinero</i>
11.45 – 12.00	PIWET and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Ewa Kwit</i>
12.00 – 12.15	Sciensano and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Elisabeth Mathijs</i>
12.15 – 12.30	VRI and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Růžek Daniel</i>
12.30 – 12.45	ANSES and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Laurent Bigarre</i>
12.45 – 13.00	SVA and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Tobias Lilja</i>
13.00 – 14.00	<i>Lunch</i>	
14.00 – 14.15	NVI and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Øivind Øines</i>
14.15 – 14.30	IZSAM and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Alessio Lorusso</i>
14.30 – 14.40	The Italian Platform for collection and sharing of microbial pathogens NGS data	<i>Adriano Di Pasquale</i>
14.40 – 14.55	IZSLER and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Ana Maria Moreno Martin</i>
14.55 – 15.10	SSI and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Maiken W. Rosenstjerne</i>
15.10 – 15.35	INSA and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Vítor Borges / Joana Isidro</i>
15.35 – 15.50	UoS and the role in the TELE-Vir project	<i>Daniel Horton</i>
15.50 – 16.00	Discussion & Workshop (different groups?)	<i>All participants</i>
16.00 – 16.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	
16.30 – 18.00	Discussion & Workshop (different groups?)	<i>All participants</i>
18.00 –	<i>Social</i>	

2.2. Meeting agenda – January 22nd 2020

TIMETABLE	TOPIC	EXPERT
09.00 – 10.00	Summary of discussion & Workshop	<i>All participants</i>
10.00 – 11.00	Strategic plan for 1 st year of TELE-Vir project	<i>All participants</i>
11.00 - 11.30	<i>Coffee break</i>	

11.30 - 12.30	<i>End of meeting</i>	<i>All participants</i>
13.00	<i>Lunch</i>	

3. Participants list

EXPERT	INSTITUTION
Vítor Borges	INSA
Joana Isidro	INSA
Elisabeth Mathijs	Sciensano
Jovita Fernández Pinero	INIA-CISA
Ewa Kwit	PIWET
Růžek Daniel	VRI
Tobias Lilja	SVA
Laurent Bigarre	ANSES
Daniel Horton	UoS
Joaquin Prada	UoS
Øivind Øines	NVI
Ana Maria Moreno Martin	IZSLER
Alessio Lorusso	IZSAM
Giovanni Savini	IZSAM
Federica Monaco	IZSAM
Cesare Cammà	IZSAM
Adriano Di Pasquale	IZSAM
Maiken Worsøe Rosenstjerne	SSI
Anders Fomsgaard	SSI
Anna Fomsgaard	SSI
Morten Rasmussen	SSI

4. Group photo

